

Spatiotemporal Analysis and Prediction of Laboratory-Generated Turbulence

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Index Terms—curvelet, multiscale analysis, convolutional neural network, turbulence

I. WHPC Lightning talk abstract

An estimated 90% of all human-generated heat is absorbed by the World’s oceans [1]; the first few meters of the oceans have as much heat capacity as the entire atmosphere [2]. The complex interactions of density-stratified fluids are a key contributor to heat transfer in the ocean, which occupies an important role in the global climate system.

Stratified fluids, like salty ocean water that is heated daily by the sun, experience a restoring force when displaced from a density equilibrium. When a less-dense fluid sinks through a more-dense fluid (e.g., warm, estuary fresh-water exchanging into cold, ocean salt-water), the less-dense fluid will experience a force to bring it back up above the heavier fluid. This mechanism drives what are called, ‘internal waves,’ referring to the behavior within the stratified-fluid interior (underneath the more visually familiar ocean-surface waves).

Internal waves are responsible for the ocean’s deep circulation and the resulting linear wave theory has been used to estimate that internal waves are responsible for terawatts ($\sim 10^{12}$, compare to average power consumption of New York City of 5.4×10^6 watts [3, table I-12b]) of energy transfer at ocean depths of 500 meters [4]. Internal waves may be amplified by various means, such as tidal flow over the ocean topology, surface winds and storms, or interactions with other internal waves [5]. Oceanic exchanges occur simultaneously and over a broad spectrum of spatial and temporal scales—making these flows very difficult to observe and understand. Outside of high-cost oceanic observational studies, researchers are limited to laboratory-scale physical experiments or numerical simulations of representative models.

One such physical experiment is the Stratified Inclined Duct (SID) [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15][in particular, see fig. 1 and §II.A from [14] for details of the setup]. A collaboration is underway with the SID experts in an effort to leverage their fastidious experimental data collection for improved experiences within broader laboratory settings.

That is, a goal of the study is to determine whether the 107 experimental shadowgraph videos collected into 349 GB of Python pickles may be used to train a novel machine learning model to automatically classify and predict the onset of mixing events, in real time, in future stratified fluid laboratories. The accurate prediction of mixing events in an experiment will permit experimentalists to prioritize relevant data (for instance, a particular moment of mixing in an experiment), minimizing the volume of data and significant storage costs. The jupyter notebooks, shell scripts, job-array techniques, and python scripts that were so far used by this project were demonstrated as an interactive visualization on how science may be enabled by modern supercomputers and their interfaces at PEARC23 in Portland [16].

The first accomplishment of this project was the successful performance of curvelet analysis on this data. The Fast Discrete Curvelet Transform, proposed by Candès and Donoho [17] and implemented in the CurveLab Matlab toolbox, utilizes a windowing approach to separate a given signal into both different scales and orientations (angles) before performing ridgelet transforms. This partitioning method improves upon the classical wavelet in the sense that it can better detect phenomena along curves, which commonly occur in Kelvin-Helmholtz waves and Holmboe waves in SID flows; the curvelet transform is therefore an ideal choice for multiscale analysis of this data. Shown in fig. 2 are the spatial domain of the curvelet transform’s coarsest and finest scales, performed on a turbulent flow. Different textures are extracted from the original image.

The second part of this work is the construction of a convolutional neural network, trained on the shadowgraph images as labeled by a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [13, 14], which found five distinct clusters of behavior in the leading two-dimensional component space: either laminar or one of four varieties of mixing or turbulence. The CNN achieved nearly 97% accuracy classifying a test set of 20% of the dataset (roughly 7,000 shadowgraph frames distributed across the experiments). The authors’ first approach to conducting spatiotemporal classification transforms the categories into the simpler, binary states of laminar (L) or turbulent (T), and trains instead on

Fig. 1. An example shadowgraph frame from one of the stratified inclined duct experiments, as indicated. At the time shown, the less-dense fluid (top-half, flowing right-to-left) and the more-dense fluid (bottom-half, flowing left-to-right) have begun to mix in a non-laminar way, resulting in the intricate, non-trivial leaf-like patterns at the two-fluid interface.

Fig. 2. (a) The original shadowgraph depicting a turbulent flow. (b) The coarsest scale. (c) The finest scale.

sequences of frames. Each sequence is labeled by two letters: the state of the current sequence, and the state of the next sequence (i.e., ‘LL’, ‘LT’, ‘TL’, and ‘TT’). Preliminary work has the experiments partitioned into sequences of ten frames which the CNN achieves roughly 87% accuracy on.

The spatiotemporal CNN has over one billion total parameters, and will likely benefit from using coefficients from the curvelet transform as input, reducing computational cost and training times [17, 18] as well as guiding the CNN’s feature selection toward more of the localized features of the shadowgraph. Other exciting objectives include porting the curvelet transform to the GPU, real-time experimental turbulence prediction, and the generalization of the CNN to new data.

Acknowledgment

We thank Adrien Lefauve for providing access to the data, and we look forward to future collaboration. We also thank Prof. Alberto Scotti for the project’s practical motivation, as well as Prof. Malena Español for her support and suggestions. Furthermore, we thank the Rocky Mountain Advanced Computing Consortium (RMACC) for supporting travel to the SC23 conference for Jade Businski after her participation in the RMACC HPC Symposium’s Student Poster Competition. We would like to acknowledge the computational and storage resources provided by ASU’s Research Computing, which made this work possible [19].

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